

Photon wave function and the electromagnetic vacuum

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Abstract

The association of the density of states theory to the vector potential quantization of the electromagnetic field leads naturally to the definition of the photon quantization volume, ascribing an intrinsic physical property to a single photon. Based upon the vector potential function with quantized amplitude, we define a photon wave function representing an amplitude probability for the photon localization normalized with respect to the quantization volume. In addition, it satisfies Maxwell's propagation equation and Schrödinger's equation with the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian as well as a Schrödinger-like equation for the vector potential.

The electromagnetic vacuum derives straightforward from the photon vector potential function and has both classical and quantum representations. It permits to remedy to the zero-point energy shortcomings and singularities in quantum electrodynamics. Finally, the photon wave function is physically related to the electromagnetic quantum vacuum states putting the basis for understanding entanglement.

Key words: photon wave function, vector potential quantization, photon quantization volume, photon *vector potential* – energy equation, electromagnetic vacuum.

1. Introduction

The photon wave function, defined as an amplitude probability for localization according to the principles of quantum theory, was always an intriguing chapter of quantum electrodynamics (QED) and raises fundamental and particularly subtle issues widely commented in the literature [1-4]. Various proposals have been advanced, all based on the electric and magnetic fields of the classical electromagnetic radiation and the Riemann-Silberstein complex vector [5-9]. However, the second quantization procedure in QED is carried out on the electromagnetic field potentials and not on the electric and magnetic fields, which both derive from the vector potential according to Maxwell's equations. Thus, the square modulus of the proposed photon wave functions based on the electric and magnetic fields is related to the energy density of the electromagnetic wave and do not represent a probability amplitude for the photon localization in a given volume, as required by the basic quantum mechanics theory. Furthermore, the electric and magnetic fields used in these formalisms are not quantized at a single photon level with corresponding precise amplitudes and the physical relationship of photons to the quantum vacuum does not appear clearly.

On the other hand, the singularities and shortcomings related to the electromagnetic field zero-point energy, resulting from the harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian in QED theory and attributed to the quantum vacuum, are well known and raise serious doubts whether it really represents a physical state. In fact, the zero-point energy term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar\omega_k / 2$, represented by the summation over the energy of all modes k and

polarizations λ , is a constant and commutes with the quantum mechanics Hermitian operators expressing measurable observables. Consequently, it has absolutely no influence to the quantum vacuum effects. For instance, the spontaneous emission probability and the Lamb shift are calculated in QED based on the properties of the single photon creation $a_{k\lambda}^+$ and annihilation $a_{k\lambda}$ non-Hermitian operators without using at all the term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar\omega_k / 2$ [10-12]. Regarding the Casimir effect, as demonstrated by many studies

[13-16], its physical origin is related to charge effects and Lorentz's forces and it is fully interpreted without invoking the zero-point energy.

Furthermore, it is well known that the zero-point energy density is infinite at any point in space and represents the principal singularity of the quantum field theory and a real cosmological problem. It strongly conflicts with recent astrophysical observations on the accelerated cosmic expansion according

to which the quantum vacuum energy density is roughly $\sim 10^{-10} J m^{-3}$ [17-22]. Even if the summation of the zero-point energy in QED is upper limited to Planck's energy ($\sim 10^{19} GeV$) the resulting vacuum energy density is approximately $\sim 10^{110} J m^{-3}$, in disagreement with the experimental estimations by a factor of 120 orders of magnitude. Many authors have characterized this unphysical discrepancy between the well-validated astrophysical observations and the theoretical calculations as "vacuum catastrophe", entailing the necessity of reconsidering the zero-point energy in quantum field theory. From a strict mathematical point of view, the electromagnetic field zero-point energy issues from the mean value of the normal ordering and antinormal ordering Hamiltonians [12,23-25] whilst there is no physical reason supporting this operation. Indeed, skipping the zero-point energy from the standard QED theory by considering the normal ordering Hamiltonian do not compromise any of the achievements related to the calculation of the vacuum effects. Finally, the experimental evidence has never demonstrated that a single photon state is a harmonic oscillator.

In this paper, starting from the electromagnetic field vector potential we establish a real photon wave function satisfying Schrödinger's equation and suitably normalized as an amplitude probability to take into account the photon quantization volume, an intrinsic physical property issued from the density of states theory. This process naturally leads to the definition of the electromagnetic vacuum complementing the standard normal ordering Hamiltonian in QED, overcoming the vacuum energy singularity as well as the shortcomings for the calculation of the vacuum effects. We also show that photons are generated from the electromagnetic vacuum while the photon wave function is physically related to the vacuum states that may be at the origin of entanglement.

2. The quantization volume V_k , an intrinsic geometrical property of photons.

Vector potential quantization at a single photon state.

Before proceeding to the formulation of the photon wave function, it is of high importance to recall briefly the main lines of the vector potential quantization in standard QED theory [10, 12]. In order to define the vector potential amplitude operators for a single k -mode and λ -polarization photon with angular frequency ω_k , the mean value over a period of the energy density of a monochromatic plane wave, expressed through the vector potential amplitude $\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k)$, is put equal to the energy density of a single photon in a cavity V

$$2\varepsilon_0\omega_k^2 |\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k)|^2 = \frac{\hbar\omega_k}{V} \rightarrow \alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} \quad (1)$$

where $\hbar$ is Planck's reduced constant and ε_0 is the vacuum electric permittivity.

Thus, the vector potential amplitude operators for a single photon in QED are defined as follows

$$\tilde{a}_{k\lambda} = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} a_{k\lambda} \quad \tilde{a}_{k\lambda}^* = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} a_{k\lambda}^+ \quad (2)$$

with $a_{k\lambda}$ and $a_{k\lambda}^+$ the annihilation and creation non-Hermitian operators respectively for a single k -mode and λ -polarization photon.

Hence, the radiation vector potential writes

$$\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t) = \sum_k \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k V}} \sum_{\lambda=1}^2 \left[\alpha_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} + \alpha_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right] \quad (3)$$

where the summations run over all the modes k and the two polarizations λ , circular left and right with $\hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}$ the corresponding complex unit vector. Also, $\vec{k}$ is the wave-vector with amplitude $|\vec{k}| = 2\pi / \lambda_k$ where λ_k is the wavelength of the mode k .

In fact, the last expression for the vector potential is obtained from the general equation established in quantum field theory

$$\bar{A}(\vec{r}, t) = \int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0\omega_k}} \sum_{\lambda=1}^2 \left[\alpha_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} + \alpha_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right] \quad (4)$$

in which the continuous summation over the modes k is transformed to a discrete one by considering the electromagnetic field in a cavity of volume V and applying the density of states theory

$$\int \frac{d^3k}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \rightarrow \sqrt{\frac{1}{V}} \sum_k \quad (5)$$

The last transformation is valid for any shape of the cavity V provided that all the photons wavelengths λ_k are much shorter than the volume characteristic dimensions.

$$\lambda_k \ll V^{1/3} \quad (\forall k) \quad (6)$$

Now, in classical electromagnetic theory the vector potential has natural units proportional to a frequency [26,27]. However, the vector potential amplitude of all the single modes in (3) depends on the inverse square root of the frequency. The physical reason of this apparent ambiguity is that, following the transformation operation (5) according to the condition (6), the vector potential expressed in (3) is only valid for a large number of photons in a cavity V .

In fact, in order to define the vector potential amplitude operators for a single photon the volume parameter V in (1) should be that corresponding to the quantization volume of a single photon state for the equation to hold physically. According to the density of states theory, taking into account the two spin values $\pm\hbar$, corresponding to circular left and right polarizations, as well as the two possible directions along the same propagation axis, the number of k -mode photons $dn(\omega_k)$ in the quantization volume V in the frequency interval between ω_k and $\omega_k + d\omega_k$ writes [12,28]

$$dn(\omega_k) = 4V \frac{\omega_k^2}{\pi^2 c^3} d\omega_k \quad (7)$$

where c is the speed of light in vacuum.

The integration of (7) entails that the quantization volume that can be ascribed to a single k -mode photon with angular frequency ω_k is

$$V_k \simeq \left(\frac{3}{4} \pi^2 c^3 \right) \omega_k^{-3} = 0.029 \lambda_k^3 \quad (8)$$

Replacing V in the equations (1) and (2) by the last expression of V_k , we get the vector potential amplitude for a single k -mode photon, which now is indeed proportional to the frequency

$$\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \xi \omega_k \quad (9)$$

and the corresponding operators

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda} = \xi \omega_k \alpha_{k\lambda} \quad ; \quad \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}^* = \xi \omega_k \alpha_{k\lambda}^+ \quad (10)$$

The vector potential amplitude constant ξ has positive and negative values and writes

$$\xi \simeq \pm \frac{1}{\pi} \sqrt{\frac{2\hbar}{3\varepsilon_0 c^3}} \quad (11)$$

Although the integration of (7) does not result to a pure integer, the last relation is an excellent approximation. A precise determination of the photon vector potential amplitude quantization constant ξ is obtained by the energy normalization of a circularly polarized monochromatic plane electromagnetic wave over a period to Planck's single photon energy $\hbar\omega_k$, getting [24,25,29-31]

$$\xi = \pm \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar}{8\alpha \varepsilon_0 c^3}} = \frac{\hbar}{4\pi e c} = \pm 1.747 \cdot 10^{-25} \text{ Volt } m^{-1} s^2 \quad (12)$$

where e is the electron or positron charge and $\alpha \simeq 1/137$ is the fine structure constant.

The resulting quantization volume involves the polarization precession of the vector potential amplitude along the propagation axis and writes

$$V_k = \left(\frac{\hbar}{2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2} \right) \omega_k^{-3} = 4\alpha \lambda_k^3 \simeq 0.029 \lambda_k^3 \quad (13)$$

which is numerically equivalent to (8).

Hence, the vector potential of a single electromagnetic k -mode can now be expressed in both classical and quantum representations through the defined vector potential amplitude

$$\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \omega_k \left[\hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} + \hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \right] = \omega_k \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (14a)$$

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \omega_k \left[\hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} a_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} + \hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda}^* a_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \theta)} \right] = \omega_k \tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (14b)$$

In what follows, we analyze explicitly the physical consequences of the established formalism, defining a photon wave function and expressing the electromagnetic vacuum for both the classical and quantum theories.

3. Photon wave-particle equation and wave function.

Both the density of states theory and the energy normalization procedure lead to a single photon quantization volume (13) which is proportional to ω_k^{-3} in agreement with the experimental observations since Mandel's works [10,12,32,33]. For a free k -mode photon, the volume V_k corresponds to the space in which the quantized vector potential precesses around the propagation axis at the angular frequency ω_k over a period, hence over a wavelength λ_k , generating orthogonal electric and magnetic fields [24,25,30] whose amplitudes are obtained respectively from Maxwell's equations

$$|\vec{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda}| = |-\partial \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) / \partial t| = \sqrt{2} |\xi| \omega_k^2 \quad ; \quad |\vec{\beta}_{k\lambda}| \propto \sqrt{2 \epsilon_0 \mu_0} |\xi| \omega_k^2 \quad (15)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum magnetic permeability.

The fact that the electric and magnetic field amplitudes of a single photon are proportional to the square of the frequency is extremely important and it has been shown that it may lead to a vacuum energy density compatible with recent astrophysical observations related to the cosmic expansion [34].

We can now express the particle properties of the photon, energy and momentum by using the classical electromagnetic functions with circular polarization integrated over the quantization volume V_k .

$$E_k = \int_{V_k} 2 \epsilon_0 \alpha_{0k}^2 \omega_k^2 d^3 r = \int_{V_k} 2 \epsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 d^3 r = 2 \epsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k = \hbar \omega_k \quad (16)$$

$$\vec{p}_k = \int_{V_k} \epsilon_0 \vec{\mathcal{E}}_{k\lambda} \times \vec{\beta}_{k\lambda} d^3 r = \epsilon_0 \left(\sqrt{2} \omega_k \alpha_{0k} \right) \left(\sqrt{2 \epsilon_0 \mu_0} \omega_k \alpha_{0k} \right) V_k \vec{k} / |\vec{k}| = \hbar \vec{k} \quad (17)$$

Consequently, the energy and momentum of a single photon are not carried by a point particle but by a three dimensional wave-corpucle. The position and momentum Hermitian operators are also expressed respectively through the quantization volume V_k [10,12]

$$\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda} = \sqrt{\epsilon_0 V_k} (\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda} + \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}^*) \quad ; \quad \tilde{P}_{k\lambda} = -i \omega_k \sqrt{\epsilon_0 V_k} (\tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda} - \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}^*) \quad (18)$$

Considering now the single photon vector potential amplitude operators expressed in (10) it is straightforward to obtain Heisenberg's commutation relation

$$\left[\tilde{Q}_{k\lambda}, \tilde{P}_{k'\lambda'} \right] = -i \epsilon_0 \omega_k^2 \omega_{k'} \sqrt{V_k V_{k'}} \left[(\xi a_{k\lambda} + \xi a_{k\lambda}^+), (\xi a_{k'\lambda'} - \xi a_{k'\lambda'}^+) \right] = i \hbar \delta_{kk'} \delta_{\lambda\lambda'} \quad (19)$$

Obviously, the photon position-momentum uncertainty, a fundamental concept in quantum theory, is an intrinsic physical property of the nature of the photon and is related to the quantization volume V_k .

Thus, the photon appears to be a particular case in the standard model of particles. Photons are not point particles and according to the wavelength, the dimensions of the photon quantization volume (13) may vary from femtometers, for high-energy γ rays, to cosmic dimensions for very low frequency radio waves. This also provides a physical explanation why a position operator cannot be defined for the photon.

Considering the angular frequency operator $\tilde{\omega}_k = -i c \vec{\nabla}_k$, the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian $\tilde{H}_k = -i \hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k$ and the vector potential amplitude operator $\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} = -i \xi c \vec{\nabla}_k$, where $\vec{\nabla}_k$ acts upon the mode k , it is straightforward to show that the vector potential (14) with the quantized amplitude satisfies Schrödinger's equation

$$i \hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \tilde{H}_k \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (20)$$

and an analogue equation for the vector potential amplitude operator

$$i\xi \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \tilde{\alpha}_{0k} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (21)$$

A synthesis of the last two symmetrical equations leads to the photon *vector potential – energy* equation, a unique equation expressing both the first (energy) and second (vector potential) quantization of the electromagnetic field

$$i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{0k}}{\tilde{H}_k} \right) \vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (22)$$

The constants ξ and $\hbar$ characterize the quantization of the photon vector potential amplitude $\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) = \xi\omega_k$ and energy $E_k(\omega_k) = \hbar\omega_k$ respectively.

Now, in quantum mechanics a wave function $\Psi(\vec{r}, t)$ is a probability amplitude related to the particle localization at the coordinate $\vec{r}$ at an instant t . The wave functions are generally normalized so as the summation of $|\Psi(\vec{r}, t)|^2$ in a given volume expresses the probability to localize the particle with a degree of confidence. According to these considerations, a wave function for the single k -mode photon can now be defined from the vector potential function $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$. In fact, the square modulus of $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is proportional to the square of the frequency

$$|\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 = \xi^2 \omega_k^2 \propto \lambda_k^{-2} \quad (23)$$

Consequently, the higher the frequency, the shorter the photon wavelength and the higher the localization probability. This is in agreement with Heisenberg's uncertainty principle as well as with the experimental evidence [10,12,32,33]. Hence, the vector potential function $\vec{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ with the quantized amplitude, which also includes the spin information through the two circular polarizations, may form the basis for defining a photon wave function. Furthermore, the experiments have shown that a single photon is localizable only within a volume proportional to λ_k^3 . Consequently, such a photon wave function has to be normalized with respect to the quantization volume V_k .

Therefore, we define the photon wave function as following [35]

$$\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k}{\hbar} \right)^{1/2} \left[\alpha_{0k}(\omega_k) \left(\hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t)} + \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t)} \right) \right] \quad (24)$$

where λ is left or right circular polarizations corresponding to spin $\pm\hbar$.

Note that $\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}^*(\vec{r}, t)$ so that $\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is a real non-local wave function and the normalization factor in the square root has been chosen so that

$$|\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 = \frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k}{\hbar} \left[\xi^2 \omega_k^2 \left(|\hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}|^2 + |\hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^*|^2 \right) \right] = \frac{2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^3}{\hbar} = \frac{1}{V_k} \quad (25)$$

Thus, for a photon emitted at an instant t_0 at the coordinate r_0 the probability to be localized at t around $r=r_0+ct$ on the propagation axis is normalized with respect to the quantization volume V_k .

$$\int |\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 d^3 r' = 1 \quad \text{within the limit} \quad \int d^3 r' \leq \int_{V_k} d^3 r' \quad (26)$$

In addition, $\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ satisfies Maxwell's propagation equation in vacuum

$$\vec{\nabla}_k^2 \vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} \vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = 0 \quad (27)$$

as well as the *vector potential – energy* photon equation

$$i \left(\frac{\xi}{\hbar} \right) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{0k}}{\tilde{H}_k} \right) \vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (28)$$

Consequently, $\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is a real non-local wave function for the photon, carrying the spin information through the circular polarizations and normalized with respect to the quantization volume.

Note that according to equations (27) and (28), due to its characteristic wave expression $\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is defined at an instant t at the coordinate r . However, the photon as an integral physical entity may only subsist within a volume V_k around r and its physical properties are obtained by integration of the wave properties over V_k according to (16) and (17). Thus, a position operator for the photon cannot be defined due to its intrinsic volume property. Through this point of view, the mean values of the quantum mechanics operators, which yield the physical observables for the point particles, can be applied with a particular way in the case of the photon by considering the quantization volume V_k .

Hence, the mean value of the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian in a single photon state writes

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | \tilde{H}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | -i\hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| \\ & = \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \left(e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} + e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right) \left(e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} - e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \right) \right| \\ & = \varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \left(e^{2i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} - e^{-2i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r}-\omega_k t)} \right) \right| = 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 V_k \left| \sin 2(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right| \\ & = \hbar \omega_k \left| \sin 2(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right| \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Note that $\left| \sin 2(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right|$ is a phase function varying from zero to one which physically means that when $\left| \sin 2(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t) \right| = 1$ corresponds to the ‘‘phase-matching’’ with the quantization volume V_k around r . In this case, the mean value of the Hamiltonian is Planck’s single photon energy $\hbar \omega_k$ and the momentum operator yields Einstein’s single photon momentum

$$\left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | \vec{p}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | -i\hbar \vec{\nabla}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{c} \quad (30)$$

The energy density for a single photon state is also readily obtained by

$$W_k = |\Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)|^2 \left| \langle \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) | \tilde{H}_k | \Phi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \rangle_{V_k} \right| = \frac{\hbar \omega_k}{V_k} = 2\varepsilon_0 \xi^2 \omega_k^4 \quad (31)$$

which is proportional to the fourth power of the frequency as in the case of a classical radiating dipole. Thus, the established photon wave function $\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ is normalized with respect to the intrinsic photon quantization volume V_k . It satisfies Maxwell’s propagation equation in vacuum, Schrödinger’s equation with the relativistic massless particle Hamiltonian $\tilde{H}_k = -i\hbar c \vec{\nabla}_k$ and a Schrödinger-like equation for the vector potential amplitude operator $\tilde{\alpha}_{0k} = -i\xi c \vec{\nabla}_k$.

4. The electromagnetic vacuum and the photon wave function

For $\omega_k = 0$, according to (14), (15) and (16) the photon vector potential, energy, electric and magnetic fields vanish. However, this zero frequency state does not correspond to an intangible and perfectly empty space because the main function $\vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ of the vector potential (14) does not vanish and reduces to the expressions

$$\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda} = \xi \left(\hat{\varepsilon}_\lambda e^{i\theta} + c c \right) \quad (32a)$$

$$\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda} = \xi \left(\hat{\varepsilon}_\lambda a_{k\lambda} e^{i\theta} + \hat{\varepsilon}_\lambda^* a_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i\theta} \right) \quad (32b)$$

In total absence of energy, of vector potential as well as of electric and magnetic fields, the zero frequency state $\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda}$ corresponds to the electromagnetic field ground state, the electromagnetic vacuum.

$\vec{\Xi}_{0\lambda}$ is a real field permeating all of space ($\lambda_k \rightarrow \infty$) with electric potential nature having positive and negative components. It is expressed in both classical and quantum representations showing that the vacuum state in the classical electromagnetic theory does exist.

Furthermore, the electromagnetic vacuum field is composed of all possible states $\Xi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ because the phase parameter θ may take any value

$$\bar{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \left(\hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} + cc \right) \quad (33a)$$

$$\tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \xi \left(\hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda} a_{k\lambda} e^{i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} + \hat{\epsilon}_{k\lambda}^* a_{k\lambda}^+ e^{-i(\vec{k}\cdot\vec{r} - \omega_k t + \phi)} \right) \quad (33b)$$

Obviously, the vacuum states $\Xi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ contain all the physical parameters characterizing a k -mode of the electromagnetic field that is, wave vector, frequency and circular polarization. Using the angular frequency operator for each mode, $\tilde{\omega}_k = -i c \vec{\nabla}_k$ we get the equation governing the vacuum states

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} = \tilde{\omega}_k \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \\ \tilde{\alpha}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

The physical significance of the last equation is of high importance, yielding that the electromagnetic vacuum states are transformed to real photons by the action of the angular frequency operator.

We can readily show that the electromagnetic vacuum, as established above, lifts the well-known QED ambiguities concerning the calculation of the spontaneous emission probability rate. In fact, the general Hamiltonian of an atom in the presence of an electromagnetic field in the dipole approximation writes in standard QED formalism

$$H_{tot} = H_{EM} + H_{int} + H_{atom} = \sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \left(a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) - \vec{D} \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) + \sum_i \hbar \omega_i |\Psi_i\rangle \langle \Psi_i| \quad (35)$$

where H_{EM} is the electromagnetic field harmonic oscillator Hamiltonian including the zero-point energy $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$, $\vec{D} = e \vec{r}$ is the dipole moment of an atomic electron with charge e and $|\Psi_i\rangle$ are the atomic levels with the corresponding energies $\hbar \omega_i$.

The spontaneous emission rate is always calculated in QED neglecting the vacuum energy $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ in the electromagnetic field Hamiltonian H_{EM} while using the following expression for the electric field $\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t)$ in the interaction Hamiltonian H_{int} , deduced from Heisenberg's equation of motion

$$\vec{E}(\vec{r}, t) = - \frac{\partial \vec{A}(\vec{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{i}{\hbar} \left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \hbar \omega_k \left(a_{k\lambda}^+ a_{k\lambda} + \frac{1}{2} \right) \right] \quad (36)$$

Obviously, with the purpose of calculating the electric field attributed to the vacuum state the term $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ should be the principal contribution in the interaction Hamiltonian H_{int} through the electric field obtained in (36). However, since the zero-point energy $\sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k$ is a constant entails that

$\left[\vec{A}(\vec{r}, t), \sum_{k,\lambda} \frac{1}{2} \hbar \omega_k \right] = 0$ and consequently this term has absolutely no contribution to the interaction

Hamiltonian used to calculate the spontaneous emission in QED.

This well-known ambiguity is due to the fact that in standard QED formalism the vacuum, that is the zero-point field, is not described by a function of $a_{k\lambda}$ and $a_{k\lambda}^+$ operators and consequently an Hamiltonian for the electron-vacuum interaction processes cannot be defined.

Conversely, the electromagnetic quantum vacuum $\tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ does indeed depend on the $a_{k\lambda}$ and $a_{k\lambda}^+$ operators permitting to define an interaction Hamiltonian per angular frequency between an electron and the vacuum states

$$H_{int} = \frac{\hbar e}{m_e c} \tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda} \tilde{\omega}_k = -i\hbar \frac{e}{m_e} \tilde{\Xi}_{k\lambda} \cdot \vec{\nabla}_k \quad (37)$$

where m_e is the electron mass.

Using first order time dependent perturbation the calculation of the spontaneous emission rate becomes now straightforward with exactly the same procedure as in standard QED theory. The amplitude of the transition probability per angular frequency between an initial state $|\Psi_i, 0\rangle$ with energy $E_i = \hbar\omega_i$ and a final state $|\Psi_f, n_{k\lambda}\rangle$ with energy $E_{f, n_{k\lambda}} = \hbar\omega_f + n_{k\lambda}\hbar\omega_k$, where $n_{k\lambda}$ is the number of photons, writes

$$c_{\omega_k}^{(1)}(t) = -\frac{e\xi}{m_e} \int_0^t \left[\langle \Psi_f, n_{k\lambda} | \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda} \cdot \vec{\nabla}_k a_{k\lambda} | \Psi_i, 0 \rangle e^{i(\omega_i - \omega_f - n_{k\lambda}\omega_k)t'} + \langle \Psi_f, n_{k\lambda} | \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \cdot \vec{\nabla}_k a_{k\lambda}^+ | \Psi_i, 0 \rangle e^{-i(\omega_i - \omega_f - n_{k\lambda}\omega_k)t'} \right] dt' \quad (38)$$

Considering Heisenberg's equation of motion $\vec{p} = m_e \frac{d}{dt} \vec{r} = -m_e \frac{i}{\hbar} [\vec{r}, H_{atom}]$ and taking into account

that $a_{k\lambda} |\Psi_i, 0\rangle = 0$ the creation operator $a_{k\lambda}^+$ scalar product writes

$$\langle \Psi_f, n_{k\lambda} | \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \cdot \vec{\nabla}_k a_{k\lambda}^+ | \Psi_i, 0 \rangle = -\delta_{1, n_{k\lambda}} m_e \omega_{if} \hat{\varepsilon}_{k\lambda}^* \cdot \vec{r}_{if} / \hbar \quad (39)$$

with $\vec{r}_{if} = \langle \Psi_f | \vec{r} | \Psi_i \rangle$ and $\omega_{if} = \omega_i - \omega_f$.

Putting $\xi = \hbar/4\pi ec$ we obtain the well-known expression for the spontaneous emission rate the spontaneous emission rate

$$W_{if} = \frac{e^2}{8\pi^2 \hbar \varepsilon_0 c^3} \omega_{if}^3 \int d\Omega \sum_{\lambda} |\vec{r}_{if}|_{\lambda}^2 \cos^2 \theta = \frac{e^2}{3\hbar c^3} \frac{1}{\pi \varepsilon_0} \omega_{if}^3 |\vec{r}_{if}|^2 \quad (40)$$

where $\cos^2 \theta$ has been replaced by the mean value $\langle \cos^2 \theta \rangle = \int \cos^2 \theta d\Omega / 4\pi = 1/3$.

Consequently, through the action of the angular frequency operator the vacuum states interact directly with the quantum levels of atoms and molecules inducing the spontaneous emission effect generating real photons.

On the other hand, the Lamb shift can be obtained exactly as in Bethe's calculation [11] by using the vector potential expression (14) while the Fulling-Davies-Unruh temperature is also readily obtained for particles accelerated in the electromagnetic vacuum field $\Xi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ [36].

Now, it is obvious that the physical basis of the photon wave function as defined in (24) lays on the electromagnetic vacuum states

$$\vec{\Phi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 \omega_k^3}{\hbar} \right)^{1/2} \vec{\Xi}_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t) \quad (41)$$

As discussed above, the electromagnetic vacuum is a universal field composed of all the $\Xi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ states at any point and consequently when a photon is created a vacuum state with the corresponding angular frequency and polarization is automatically depleted at the creation coordinate. Consequently, immediately after this process the oncoming creation of a new photon with the same angular frequency yields the depleting of a vacuum state with opposite polarization. This process is distance independent and puts the basis for understanding the entangled states.

Conclusions

Without stating postulates or advancing assumptions, the coupling of the density of states theory to the vector potential quantization ascribes a quantization volume V_k to single photons, an intrinsic geometrical parameter, permitting the definition of a photon wave function normalized precisely with respect to V_k .

The quantum properties of a photon, energy and momentum, are not carried by a point particle but by the whole single period wave-packet in the quantization volume V_k whose dimensions, depending on the wavelength, may vary from cubic femtometers to cosmic scales. This is precisely the physical reason why a position operator cannot be defined for a single photon and we have shown that Heisenberg's position-momentum uncertainty lays precisely on its intrinsic volume characteristic.

Based on the vector potential function with the quantized amplitude $\xi\omega_k$ a photon wave function has been established including the two spin values $\pm\hbar$, corresponding to circular left and right polarization. It satisfies Maxwell's propagation equation in vacuum as well as the photon vector potential – energy equation resuming the first and second quantization of the electromagnetic field. It represents a localization probability amplitude and the spatial integration of its square modulus is normalized with respect to V_k .

When the frequency tends to zero, the limit of the vector potential function principal part $\Xi_{k\lambda}(\vec{r}, t)$ leads naturally to the electromagnetic vacuum, a zero-energy field, with positive and negative components, filling the whole space and which is expressed in both the classical electromagnetic and quantum theories. It is composed of states with all possible frequencies and polarizations. This quantum vacuum representation naturally complements the normal ordering Hamiltonian and remedies to all the drawbacks and ambiguities resulting from the harmonic oscillator zero-point energy in QED. The vacuum is now expressed through the single photon creation and annihilation non-Hermitian operators and consequently the calculation of the spontaneous emission becomes straightforward. In addition, the infinite energy vacuum singularity is lifted and, as demonstrated previously, the calculated vacuum energy density is comparable to the well-validated observations.

Thus, photons are neither point particles nor harmonic oscillators and constitute a particular case in the standard particle model.

The established photon wave function depends directly on the vacuum states with identical frequency, wave-vector and polarization. We may assume that the depleting of a vacuum state at a given frequency and polarization generating a photon with the same physical properties imply that the oncoming next photon generation at the same frequency will have opposite polarization. This process is distance independent and may be at the origin of the entangled states.

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